

Fig1G,I**L2/3 PNs recordings C57BL/6J mouse line**

Rhythmic Paired Stimulation (RPS)

injections

Pom: AAV1-CAG-hChr2-H134R-tdTomato

n=8 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs pre	Cm	Fig 1G		Fig 1I	
							Pre L4_PSP	Post L4_PSP	Pre Pom_PSP	Post Pom_PSP
1	1.26.16	1	C57BL/6J	1.6.16	31.00	117.31	1.1567	1.3081	0.4554	0.3481
2	2.3.16	2	C57BL/6J	1.13.16	30.20	63.58	1.6818	2.8504	0.3132	0.5136
3	2.1.16	1	C57BL/6J	1.6.16	30.20	88.00	1.4685	0.9284	0.4319	0.2515
4	2.23.16	1	C57BL/6J	2.4.16	38.60	84.74	0.7420	1.6577	0.3569	0.3112
5	2.23.16	2	C57BL/6J	2.4.16	38.70	76.64	1.7280	2.6464	0.3668	1.4903
6	2.22.16	2	C57BL/6J	2.4.16	29.20	137.99	2.7595	7.0266	1.1309	0.8410
7	2.24.16	1	C57BL/6J	2.4.16	38.70	137.99	0.9078	4.6523	0.2901	0.4192
8	2.24.16	2	C57BL/6J	2.4.16	28.40	126.77	0.7953	1.8853	0.3887	0.3180

Fig1K,M**L2/3 PNs recordings C57BL/6J mouse line**

Rhythmic Paired Stimulation (RPS) & Clozapine N-oxide (CNO)

injections

Pom: AAV2-hSyn-HA-hM4D(Gi)-IRES-mCitrine

AAV1-CAG-hChr2-H134R-tdTomato

							Fig1K, n= 11 mice		Fig1M, n=4 mice	
MM.DD.YY							Pom failure rate		Avg. L4 PSP (mV)	
cell #	Date	cell	genotype	injections	Rs	Cm	Pre CNO	Post CNO	Pre	Post
1	8.5.16	1	C57BL/6J	7.20.16	15.90	124.27	12.50	35.71	4.6666	2.1653
2	8.5.16	2	C57BL/6J	7.20.16	25.90	112.60	8.33	9.09	1.0654	1.0493
3	8.8.16	1	C57BL/6J	7.20.16	37.70	156.90	0.00	0.00	2.3669	0.9995
4	8.8.16	2	C57BL/6J	7.20.16	32.80	155.97	0.00	0.00	2.1026	1.1274
5	10.2.16	1	C57BL/6J	9.22.16	13.60	65.30	18.18	11.11	1.6805	0.9175
6	10.18.16	1	C57BL/6J	10.6.16	38.00	51.17	36.36	56.25	1.1129	1.2837
PicROTOXIN (100µM)										
1	6.30.15	1	C57BL/6J	6.10.15	22.70	35.34	0.00	12.50		
2	7.13.15	1	C57BL/6J	6.23.15	34.00	116.71	0.00	0.00		
3	7.15.15	2	C57BL/6J	6.23.15	21.60	78.92	0.00	7.14		
4	7.24.15	2	C57BL/6J	7.7.15	31.30	83.48	9.09	38.46		
5	8.24.15	2	C57BL/6J	8.11.15	35.80	139.35	30.00	37.50		
6	9.29.15	1	C57BL/6J	9.17.15	35.60	51.84	0.00	0.00		
7	8.18.15	1	C57BL/6J	8.11.15	33.80	55.92	50.00	70.00		

Fig2B,D**L2/3 PNs recordings C57BL/6J mouse line**

Rhythmic Paired Stimulation (RPS)

injections

Pom: AAV1-CAG-hChR2-H134R-tdTomato

<i>n=9 mice</i> PicROTOXIN (100μM) MM.DD.YY							Fig2B	
cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs	Cm	Pre RPS Avg L4 PSP	Post
1	4.8.15	1	C57BL/6J	4.9.15	21.70	88.89	2.7323	3.9819
2	4.22.15	1	C57BL/6J	3.20.15	25.50	45.55	0.4707	0.6628
3	5.5.15	1	C57BL/6J	4.14.15	30.00	35.00	1.6574	2.8126
4	6.1.15	1	C57BL/6J	5.14.15	4.00	37.00	0.4777	1.4991
5	6.1.15	2	C57BL/6J	5.14.15	18.20	36.38	0.8958	1.7688
6	6.25.15	1	C57BL/6J	6.10.15	33.10	57.90	0.9227	1.0526
7	7.23.15	1	C57BL/6J	7.7.15	37.00	56.00	1.2125	3.2900
8	9.14.15	1	C57BL/6J	9.2.15	27.60	74.58	1.6159	5.8136
9	9.15.15	1	C57BL/6J	9.2.15	39.00	132.00	0.7276	4.5584
10	3.7.16	1	C57BL/6J	2.17.16	38.20	76.40	0.6891	1.1050

<i>n=5 mice</i> PicROTOXIN & DAP5 (50μM)							Fig2D	
cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs	Cm	Pre RPS Avg L4 PSP	Post
1	5.28.16	1	C57BL/6J	5.14.15	14.70	39.57	1.9753	1.8228
2	6.2.15	1	C57BL/6J	5.20.15	20.60	69.83	0.1942	0.2316
3	6.26.15	1	C57BL/6J	6.10.15	18.30	45.53	0.3614	0.4317
4	7.24.15	1	C57BL/6J	7.7.15	14.00	44.00	0.7327	1.0605
5	8.12.15	3	C57BL/6J	7.21.15	26.30	83.87	1.5801	1.9336
6	8.12.15	1	C57BL/6J	7.21.15	37.00	93.16	0.8407	1.2444

Fig2G**L2/3 PNs recordings C57BL/6J mouse line**

Rhythmic Whisker Stimulation all whiskers (8Hz, 10min) followed by RPS injections

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChR2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA
AAV9.CMV5.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=6 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs	Cm	Fig2G	
							Pre RPS Avg L4 PSP	Post RPS
1	10.14.16	1	C57BL/6J	9.22.16	26.90	84.80	0.6471	0.5464
2	10.19.16	1	C57BL/6J	9.28.16	21.40	67.27	2.3932	0.7127
3	10.19.16	2	C57BL/6J	9.28.16	37.40	75.80	0.5636	0.8174
4	10.20.16	1	C57BL/6J	9.28.16	38.30	52.70	1.7437	2.0541
5	10.21.16	1	C57BL/6J	9.28.16	25.40	73.13	0.6682	1.1386
6	12.20.16	1	C57BL/6J	10.6.16	17.50	215.72	0.8384	0.7284
7	12.19.16	1	C57BL/6J	10.6.16	16.70	160.33	1.4351	1.6466

Fig3C,D

VIP interneurons recordings VIP.Cre mouse line

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChR2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=11 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs	Cm	Fig3C PS= Paired : Predicted PS (PomPSP +L4PSP)				Fig3D								
							Pom_PSP	L4_PSP	PS_PSP	Predicted PS	Pom_Total stims	Pom spikes	L4_Total stims	L4 spikes	PS_Total stims	PS spikes	Pom_spike%	L4_spike%	PS_spike%
1	6.21.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.21.16	27.70	45.58	0.6401	0.9648	1.6652	1.6049	4	0	13	7	5	4	0.00	54.00	80.00
2	6.27.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.8.16	20.20	42.21	1.3032	1.7973	2.2949	3.1005	13	0	90	2	5	1	0.00	2.20	20.00
3	6.17.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.6.16	25.70	75.22	0.3725	0.5782	0.7605	0.9507	100	2	90	2	1	1	2.00	2.20	50.00
4	6.29.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.8.16	30.00	45.00	0.6358	0.6139	0.7481	1.2497	12	0	70	3	10	1	0.00	4.30	1.00
5	8.9.16	1	VIP.Cre	7.21.16	25.30	48.10	0.8190	2.5602	3.9096	3.3792	10	2	40	24	4	3	20.00	60.00	75.00
6	6.27.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.8.16	20.20	42.21	0.3866	0.9942	0.9074	1.3808	4	0	60	1	100	1	0.00	1.66	1.00
7	12.6.16	1	VIP.Cre	11.23.16	25.10	43.14	0.5711	1.1031	1.2471	1.6742	25	7	10	0	57	10	28.00	0.00	17.54
8	5.16.18	2	VIP.Cre	4.27.18	37.50	32.89	0.9466	8.8857	15.9448	9.8323	9	0	15	9	16	16	0.00	60.00	100.00
9	6.13.18	1	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	20.90	91.47	0.5971	4.6797	5.6209	5.2768	4	0	11	5	10	5	0.00	45.00	50.00
10	6.13.18	2	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	33.10	47.10	0.4105	3.7635	4.7866	4.1740	No spiking								
11	6.13.18	3	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	19.20	17.67	1.0283	3.3876	3.2640	4.4158	5	0	15	13	14	10	0.00	86.67	71.42
12	6.15.18	1	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	36.80	18.90	1.1519	3.5471	4.5631	4.6989	No spiking								
13	6.15.18	2	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	30.00	66.00	1.1535	3.7952	4.6389	4.9487	5	0	8	0	17	6	0.00	0.00	35.29
14	6.18.18	1	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	31.20	28.43	0.8207	3.0496	3.0179	3.8703	No spiking								
15	6.18.18	2	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	19.80	126.03	0.7105	1.1246	1.2795	1.8350	6	0	14	2	15	3	0.00	14.29	20.00
16	6.18.18	3	VIP.Cre	5.30.18	40.00	56.11	0.3151	2.0211	2.4156	2.3362	3	0	6	1	6	5	0.00	16.67	83.33

Fig3G,H

SST interneurons recordings SST.Cre mouse line

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChr2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMVvs.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=9 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	injections	Rs	Cm	Fig3G				Fig3G				Pom_Total stims	Pom spikes	L4_Total stims	L4 spikes	PS_Total stim	PS spikes	Fig3H		
							Pom_PSP	L4_PSP	PS_PSP	Predicted PS	Pom_PSP	L4_PSP	PS_PSP	Predicted PS							Pom_spike%	L4_spike%	PS_spike%
1	5.26.16	1	SST.Cre	5.2.16	15.40	42.80	0.4783	3.3092	0.0000	3.7875	-0.6534	-1.3537	-7.0221	-2.0071	6	0	32	9	14	2	0.00	28.13	14.28
2	7.14.16	1	SST.Cre	6.15.16	18.50	26.50	3.0209	3.0901	2.6613	6.1110	0.0000	0.0000	-5.0266	0.0000	21	3	46	3	67	6	14.29	6.52	8.96
3	7.13.16	1	SST.Cre	6.15.16	35.40	94.12	0.5816	3.0100	0.0000	3.5916	0.0000	-0.4087	-2.3613	-0.4087	No spiking								
4	2.3.17	1	SST.Cre	1.26.17	26.70	17.18	1.1626	1.3880	1.2554	2.5506	-1.0263	-0.7335	-1.2329	-1.7598	7	0	17	7	25	1	0.00	41.00	4.00
5	2.6.17	1	SST.Cre	1.26.17	38.10	26.88	0.8172	0.8709	0.8189	1.6881	-0.7384	-0.9852	-1.0418	-1.7236	10	0	5	2	18	1	0.00	20.00	5.56
6	5.23.18	1	SST.Cre	5.9.18	22.00	42.73	0.4955	3.4197	3.1866	3.9153	-0.2960	-0.6631	-1.0306	-0.9590	No spiking								
7	5.23.18	2	SST.Cre	5.9.18	16.50	43.73	1.4027	6.3112	5.8016	7.7139	-0.4918	-0.6957	-1.8007	-1.1874	13	0	15	4	18	0	0.00	26.67	0.00
8	5.23.18	3	SST.Cre	5.9.18	22.30	41.72	0.6207	1.4035	1.3472	2.0242	0.0000	-0.4055	-0.4456	-0.4055	5	0	12	6	13	2	0.00	50.00	15.38
9	5.29.18	1	SST.Cre	5.9.18	30.20	42.04	1.9660	4.1749	2.6816	6.1409	-2.5151	-0.8234	-2.0224	-3.3385	No spiking								
10	5.29.18	2	SST.Cre	5.9.18	16.30	ND	0.6822	3.3168	3.3507	3.9990	0.0000	-1.6827	-2.3183	-1.6827	No spiking								
11	6.29.18	1	SST.Cre	6.14.18	30.90	71.23	0.3840	2.1629	2.3036	2.5469	0.0000	0.0000	-1.9113	0.0000	No spiking								
12	7.3.18	1	SST.Cre	6.14.18	13.40	43.92	0.5487	0.0000	0.0000	0.5487	0.0000	-2.5973	-1.7702	-2.5973	8	0	12	7	9	2	0.00	66.67	22.00
13	7.3.18	2	SST.Cre	6.14.18	17.80	148.00	0.9805	3.6727	3.5227	4.6531	-0.5388	0.0000	0.0000	-0.5388	10	0	12	6	15	6	0.00	50.00	40.00
14	7.3.18	5	SST.Cre	6.14.18	20.00	129.35	1.0762	3.1167	3.0215	4.1929	-1.2378	0.0000	0.0000	-1.2378	No spiking								

*ND=Not Done

Fig3K,L

PV interneurons recordings PV.Cre mouse line

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChR2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.s.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n= 6 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs	Cm	Fig3K				Pom_Total stims	Pom spikes	L4_Total stims	L4 spikes	PS_Total stims	PS spikes	Fig3L		
							Pom_PSP	L4_PSP	PS_PSP	Predicted PS							Pom_spike%	L4_spike%	PS_spike%
1	7.19.18	1	PV.Cre	6.20.18	45.16	45.16	0.3383	3.1546	4.3905	3.4929	5	0	7	3	17	11	0	42.86	64.71
2	7.24.18	1	PV.Cre	6.20.18	14.80	78.76	3.3793	2.9391	4.9439	7.8829	12	0	5	3	5	5	0	60.00	100.00
3	7.26.18	1	PV.Cre	6.21.18	22.60	36.80	0.6451	2.5407	2.3348	3.1858	11	0	8	3	8	7	0	37.50	87.50
4	7.27.18	1	PV.Cre	6.21.18	27.30	57.80	0.3760	3.1939	2.8592	3.5699	11	0	10	10	10	8	0	100.00	80.00
5	7.27.18	2	PV.Cre	6.21.18	25.70	35.00	0.3599	1.9408	2.0613	2.3007	10	0	10	1	10	8	0	10.00	80.00
6	7.30.18	1	PV.Cre	6.21.19	19.30	20.05	1.0857	3.9733	4.5685	5.0590	5	0	8	0	12	2	0	0.00	16.67
7	7.30.18	2	PV.Cre	6.21.18	19.40	41.17	0.5997	3.3758	2.8975	3.9755	4	0	11	6	10	5	0	54.54	50.00
8	8.3.18	1	PV.Cre	7.23.18	17.40	54.43	3.2959	2.6518	3.8913	3.8913	11	2	10	0	8	3	18	0.00	37.50
9	8.3.18	2	PV.Cre	7.23.18	30.90	45.59	1.3013	2.7040	3.9308	4.0054	9	0	10	6	8	9	0	60.00	89.89

Fig4C,D**L2/3 PN recordings SST.Cre mouse line**

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChr2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.Pi.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=7 mice RPS		MM.DD.YY				Fig4C		Fig4D	
cell #	Date	cell	Injections	Rs	Cm	Pre CNO L4_PSP	Post CNO L4_PSP	Pre CNO Pom_PSP	Post CNO Pom_PSP
1	5.3.16	3	4.20.16	27.2	80.61	2.6099	4.1758	ND	
2	5.25.16	1	5.2.16	17.00	54.16	ND		0.4487	0.7670
3	7.4.16	1	6.15.16	31.00	75.00	2.0667	3.2417	0.5425	0.5654
4	7.6.16	1	6.15.16	23.70	48.90	1.2384	2.6412	0.7882	1.2839
5	7.6.16	2	6.15.16	17.50	52.61	1.8987	4.7714	0.6713	1.3923
6	7.6.16	3	6.15.16	30.20	60.65	0.7544	1.5690	0.4234	0.5145
7	7.7.16	1	6.15.16	16.10	153.02	0.8909	0.9810	0.9113	0.9653
No RPS									
8	2.3.17	3	1.26.17	15.50	110.84	1.3782	1.9940	0.4007	0.3876
9	2.3.17	4	1.26.17	19.80	79.70	1.0552	1.1430	0.4472	0.6236
10	2.9.17	1	1.26.17	17.90	109.79	1.2172	1.2760	0.3930	0.5509

*ND=Not Done

Fig4G,H**L2/3 PN recordings VIP.Cre mouse line**

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChR2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV5.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

MM.DD.YY

n=11 mice RPS

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	Injections	Rs	Cm	Fig4G		Fig4H	
							Pre CNO L4_PSP	Post CNO L4_PSP	Pre CNO Pom_PSP	Post CNO Pom_PSP
1	2.8.16	2	VIP.Cre	2.8.16	15.30	58.14	1.3268	0.9266	0.3921	0.3881
2	3.1.16	1	VIP.Cre	2.12.16	40.00	110.00	0.8423	1.0757	0.4125	0.5046
3	3.2.16	1	VIP.Cre	2.12.16	20.00	58.39	0.6700	0.4390	0.4057	0.3066
4	4.21.16	2	VIP.Cre	4.9.16	23.80	42.30	1.9468	2.2778	0.7762	0.7263
5	6.1.16	1	VIP.Cre	5.23.16	33.70	45.93	1.2354	1.7598	0.4852	0.3381
6	6.17.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.6.16	30.00	88.87	0.5765	0.8514	0.4107	0.4148
7	6.18.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.6.16	30.10	57.23	1.0506	0.9134	0.9384	0.5008
NO RPS										
8	6.17.16	2	VIP.Cre	6.6.16	25.70	75.22	0.5258	1.2396	0.4418	0.4025
9	6.27.16	2	VIP.Cre	6.8.16	33.80	85.15	0.6597	1.2351	0.9131	0.5033
10	6.24.16	2	VIP.Cre	6.6.16	16.90	170.39	0.7979	1.4478	0.5303	0.4933
11	6.28.16	1	VIP.Cre	6.6.16	17.40	89.98	0.8627	1.0063	0.3997	0.2763
12	8.10.16	1	VIP.Cre	7.21.19	16.10	112.09	0.8258	0.7548	0.4072	0.3906

Fig4N,O**L2/3 PN recordings VIP.Cre mouse line**

Voltage Clamp Recordings

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChR2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=3 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Ephys Date	cell	genotype	injection date	Rs	Cm	Fig4M								Fig4O	
							Pre CNO PS_PSC (pA)				Post CNO PS_PSC (pA)				Gi	
							-70	-50	-30	0	-70	-50	-30	0	Pre CNO	Post CNO
1	1.8.18	1	VIP.Cre	12.8.17	24.10	58.38	-1.7828	5.2372	16.4662	26.3786	-0.9460	6.6084	19.2777	29.6250	40.0645	47.3733
2	1.8.18	2	VIP.Cre	12.8.18	32.10	146.72	-1.9257	8.0294	23.9174	36.2274	-1.4590	6.7277	20.9451	39.3713	92.9133	94.2645
3	1.9.18	1	VIP.Cre	12.8.19	17.20	130.62	-0.9072	2.2111	5.2927	8.2082	-2.0137	0.8634	8.1706	9.7678	12.4357	33.5070
4	1.9.18	3	VIP.Cre	12.8.20	10.60	171.55	-0.6364	1.5308	8.0780	15.9906	-0.8361	ND	ND	30.7288	34.7096	46.3057
5	1.19.18	1	VIP.Cre	1.4.18	35.20	88.70	-1.4068	2.9949	5.7809	9.4468	-2.2866	3.2027	5.4214	16.3738	22.0001	51.9969
6	1.19.18	2	VIP.Cre	1.4.19	32.10	146.72	-1.2556	3.5579	6.1122	18.3653	-1.8044	3.0962	9.1565	24.6196	61.8762	86.3514
7	1.19.18	3	VIP.Cre	1.4.20	24.90	78.28	-1.9714	0.1135	3.8651	10.2322	-2.2643	-0.0048	4.9326	14.3536	40.7250	54.1206

Fig5C**L2/3 PN recordings SST.Cre mouse line**

+ Clozapine N-oxide (CNO)

RPS

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChR2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.s.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=6 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Ephys Date	cell	genotype	injection date	Rs	Cm	Fig5C	
							Pre L4_PSP	Post L4_PSP
1	5.3.16	3	SST.Cre	4.20.16	27.20	80.61	3.3225	5.6935
2	7.4.16	1	SST.Cre	6.15.16	31.00	75.00	2.7964	3.1011
3	7.6.16	1	SST.Cre	6.15.17	23.70	48.57	2.4321	2.8861
4	7.6.16	2	SST.Cre	6.15.18	17.50	52.61	4.1005	7.5456
5	7.6.16	3	SST.Cre	6.15.19	30.20	60.65	1.4198	4.1090
6	7.7.16	1	SST.Cre	6.15.20	16.10	53.02	0.9652	1.0030
7	5.28.18	1	SST.Cre	5.9.18	15.00	69.54	1.2488	1.4678
8	5.25.16	1	SST.Cre	5.2.16	17.00	54.16	0.6978	0.8210

Fig5G**L2/3 PN recordings VIP.Cre mouse line**

+ Clozapine N-oxide (CNO)

RPS

injections

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChr2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.Pi.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=7 mice MM.DD.YY

cell #	Ephys Date	genotype	cell	injection date	Rs	Cm	Fig5G	
							Pre L4	Post L4
1	2.8.16	VIP.Cre	2	1.21.16	15.30	58.14	0.9120	0.8135
2	3.1.16	VIP.Cre	1	2.12.16	40.00	110.00	0.9800	0.8180
3	3.2.16	VIP.Cre	1	2.12.16	20.00	58.39	0.5056	0.4992
4	4.21.16	VIP.Cre	2	5.7.16	23.80	42.30	2.3521	1.7276
5	6.1.16	VIP.Cre	1	5.23.16	33.10	45.93	1.4651	1.0484
6	6.17.16	VIP.Cre	1	6.6.16	30.00	88.87	0.7175	0.8840
7	6.18.16	VIP.Cre	1	6.6.16	30.10	57.23	0.9685	0.6224

Fig5J**L2/3 PN recordings PV.Cre mouse line**

+ Clozapine N-oxide (CNO)

RPS

injections:

BC: AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom: AAV5-EF1a-double floxed-hChr2(H134R)- EYFP-WPRE-HGHpA

AAV9.CMV.s.PI.Cre.rBG (1:1)

n=6 mice MM.DD.YY

							Fig5J	
cell #	Ephys Date	cell	Genotype	injection date	Rs	Cm	Pre L4	Post L4
1	3.9.18	1	PV.Cre	2.22.18	27.50	123.98	2.7231	5.0388
2	3.12.18	1	PV.Cre	2.22.18	17.70	86.67	1.8536	1.5261
3	4.23.18	1	PV.Cre	4.6.18	18.90	100.64	2.9647	2.9478
4	4.23.18	2	PV.Cre	4.6.18	18.90	100.64	4.3439	8.3516
5	4.24.18	1	PV.Cre	4.6.18	25.70	57.11	3.3711	2.6692
6	7.6.18	1	PV.Cre	6.21.18	37.10	98.27	3.6168	4.6258
7	7.17.18	1	PV.Cre	6.27.18	35.80	64.83	4.1763	3.8421

Fig5L**L2/3 PN recordings SST.Cre mouse line**

+ Clozapine N-oxide (CNO)

RPS

injections

BC AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

Pom AAV8-hSyn-DIO-hM4D(Gi)-mCherry

n=5 mice MM.DD.YY

Fig5L

cell #	Date	cell	genotype	injection date	Rs	Cm	Pre L4	Post L4
1	11.2.17	2	SST.Cre	10.20.17	30.00	104.51	2.0493	3.3144
2	11.2.17	3	SST.Cre	10.20.17	18.30	58.90	0.7619	0.8214
3	11.3.17	3	SST.Cre	10.20.17	25.20	58.90	1.3003	1.6181
4	1.8.17	2	SST.Cre	12.4.17	16.60	127.07	1.7959	2.3912
5	1.22.18	1	SST.Cre	1.10.18	19.50	52.81	3.8175	1.2801
6	1.22.18	2	SST.Cre	1.10.18	17.40	100.84	1.9598	2.1551
7	1.23.18	1	SST.Cre	1.10.18	14.20	100.00	2.0358	2.7918